

Improvements of Knowledge Acquisition by Changing Teaching and Learning Methods

Christina Schwarz, Maximilian Bauer

Faculty of Mathematics, Physics and Computer Sciences, University of Bayreuth

Abstract

During the first year of engineering undergraduate degree programmes, students are expected to develop a profound understanding of mathematics. This requires both time and a willingness to practice on the part of the students. Unfortunately, it has been observed for several years that fewer and fewer students attend lectures and participate in the provided exercises. The prevailing trend is towards short-term preparation of course material shortly before the respective exam, resulting in generally poor exam performances and limited transfer of knowledge to long-term memory.

Based on our experience in the mathematical education for engineering students in recent years, we present our current changes to our teaching and learning methods. By revising the grading scheme and the examination format, we aim to improve examination results and better prepare students for the remainder of their studies.

Introduction

Mathematical training in engineering degree programmes typically occurs in the first year, providing the foundation for many subsequent disciplines such as electrical engineering, engineering mechanics or fluid mechanics. The primary goal of mathematical education is to impart a high level of mathematical knowledge and to foster a deep and long-lasting understanding. Alongside lectures, exercises and tutorials are designed to convey knowledge and promote a deeper understanding of the mathematical concepts and their interconnections. Regular practice throughout the term is essential to reinforce the material and enhance comprehension, cf. Brown, Roediger and McDaniel (2014).

Unfortunately, many first-year engineering students do not recognise the importance of this basic mathematical training and often see it merely as an unnecessary burden. As a result, they engage little with the underlying mathematical concepts, and do not attend or participate actively in lectures and exercises, tending instead to study only for the exam and favouring short-term exam preparation. In recent years, this trend has led towards a decline in the acquisition of mathematical knowledge. Consequently, the knowledge fails to be transferred into long-term memory and is lacking in advanced engineering courses, cf. Roediger and Butler (2011).

In order to counteract this trend, we have revised our teaching and learning methods starting from the winter term 24/25. These changes are inspired by established international systems that incorporate multiple assessments throughout the term. To encourage continuous engagement and to keep students motivated during the whole term, we are introducing several smaller examinations during the semester in addition to the final examination at the end of the term. As a result, we expect more consistent and active participation in the entire course, leading to improved exam results and a deeper understanding of the material.

In the following sections, we will outline our changes and describe our experiences with the help of initial statistical analyses. Particular attention is paid to the correlation between the changes and the performance in the exam. At the end, some impressions of students are discussed and a conclusion is drawn.

Changes in Teaching and Learning Methods

Two major changes were implemented for the winter term 24/25. The first involves continuous assessments throughout the term, and the second concerns the structure of the final exam:

- **Continuous assessments throughout the term:** Until 2024, students could voluntarily submit their exercise sheets (homework) for correction, allowing them to identify their mistakes and receive individual feedback. However, only about 15% of all students took advantage of this opportunity. Starting from the winter semester 24/25, submission and passing (without grade) of weekly homework became mandatory. In addition to the final written exam, students are now required to achieve an average score of at least 40% across all assignments throughout the term to pass the module examination, cf. Sotala and Crede (2021).
- **Restructuring of the final written exam:** As the written exam usually followed a standardised format with always similar types of tasks, many students prepared by simply reworking past exams questions. To reduce this predictability, exams are now designed with an increased variety in task types and also include additional comprehension questions.

Since the changes also affected examination modalities, the examination and study regulations were revised and came into effect for first-year students in the winter term 24/25. This naturally resulted in two test groups of students: one with mandatory assignments (mainly first-year students) and one with voluntary assignments (older students), which are distinguished accordingly in the following discussion and can be used to analyse the effects of the changes.

Assignments

During the winter term 24/25, there were 13 weekly assignments each containing 3 to 5 tasks. As shown in Figure 1, submission rates were generally 90% or higher, with a few exceptions. Assignment 9 coincided with the Christmas break; and the decrease in the submission rates for the last two assignments is attributed to some students having already accumulated enough points to reach the 40% requirement. The overall high submission rate indicates that not only the group of mandatory assignments, but also the group of voluntary assignments submitted their work.

In Figure 1, it can be observed that most students performed quite well in the assignments. In particular, a bonus task in the final assignment allowed as many students as possible to pass. Furthermore, we can see that some subjects were better understood by students than others, likely due to varying levels of difficulty across the mathematical topics and the tasks themselves. This might be taken into account in future terms.

The overall aim of these compulsory exercises was to promote understanding through continuous and intensive engagement with the subject matter throughout the term, in order to improve performance in the final exam, and to better prepare students for advanced courses. Our intention is to motivate students, rather than impose a significant obstacle. Having most students passing these assignments while observing an increased attendance and more active participation in both lectures and exercises indicates the success of our strategy.

Figure 1. Distribution of assignment results over the winter term 2024/2025. The size of the circles indicates the number of submissions with the respective result.

Restructuring of Final Exams

The written exam was designed to maintain the same level of difficulty as in previous years, but with a greater variety of task types and topics. This included the introduction of new task formats and an increased proportion of comprehension-based questions. Specifically, the exam comprised two standard tasks, similar to those in previous exams (tasks 1 and 2 in Figure 2), four tasks of new type (tasks 3, 6, 7 and 8), and three tasks classified as comprehension questions (tasks 4, 5 and 9). While performance on the standard tasks was relatively consistent, there were greater variations in the comprehension tasks. These fluctuations suggest that students either fully understood and prepared for the respective topics, or not at all - except for task 9, which consisted of multiple independent short questions of different difficulty.

Overall, however, the exam results fell short of expectations. The reasons for this are assumed to be continued low attendance in lectures and too much focus on only practicing previous exams, rather than engaging with the broader range of material.

Figure 2. Results within the different tasks of the exam. The size of the circles indicates the number of students with the respective result.

Correlation between Assignments and Exam Results

In this section the correlation between the assignment performance and the respective exam result will be discussed, see Figure 3. In the graph, the different colours indicate the two test groups: blue represents students with mandatory assignments, while red corresponds to those with voluntary assignments. Additionally, dots represent students with active participation (i.e. at least 5 weekly assignments were submitted), whereas crosses indicate inactive participation. This distinction helps to filter out students who did not make a serious attempt to pass the assignments, consisting primarily of those in the voluntary assignments group.

The following positive conclusions can be drawn from Figure 3:

- The better the assignment performance, the better the exam scores, see black regression line.
- Almost no one passed the exam without passing the assignments.
- Almost every student, who actively tried to solve the assignments, also passed them. This aligns with the initial intention to motivate continuous study rather than create a significant obstacle.
- The exam passing rate is substantially higher among students with mandatory assignments (50%), compared to only 25% in the group with voluntary assignments.

Figure 3. Correlation between assignment and exam results.

An additional survey conducted in one lecture (though not fully representative) indicates that the exam pass rate is even higher (60%) among students who actually attend and participate in the lectures. We assume a correlation whereby mainly first-year-students taking the course for the first time actually attend lectures regularly, while others (such as those who have already attended the course in the past or who only need to pass it as condition) are absent. In summary, active attendance during the current term appears to have a positive impact on exam success.

Despite all the positive conclusions, Figure 3 also reveals one significant concern. Although most of the students performed well in the assignments, many of them were unable to transfer this performance to the exam. This discrepancy suggests that some students may have copied solutions from others or relied on generative artificial intelligence to complete the assignments. Unfortunately, it is still unclear how to effectively address this issue.

While it may be necessary to accept that some students may never engage despite all effort, we can still aim to motivate most students by sharing the results of this study. Emphasizing that the assignments are manageable, even when solving them without assistance or external help, can encourage students to try solving them on their own. Furthermore, highlighting the clear correlation between assignment and exam performance may motivate students to use the assignments as effective preparation for the exam.

Impressions from Students

In addition to the perspective of the teaching staff, the students' views on the changes should also be considered. For this reason, a survey was conducted among the participants in the last lecture of the winter term 24/25. As Figure 4 shows, the feedback from the students was very positive. Furthermore, there were also direct comments requesting to maintain the compulsory assignments. It is encouraging to see that students appreciate being motivated by mandatory exercises and recognise that without this obligation, they tend to be less motivated.

Figure 4. Impressions from students.

Conclusions and Future Prospects

The changes in our teaching methods resulted in some positive effects, such as an increased motivation among students and active participation in class, as well as a high submission rate for the assignments.

Interestingly, students need to be encouraged, or even compelled, to engage continuously with mathematics, as they rarely do so voluntarily. Our study shows that students tend to study primarily for grades and only engage with homework when mandatory, rather than for their own long-term understanding. However, they also acknowledge that consistent engagement with mathematical topics, though demanding and exhausting, is valuable.

However, the examination results still fell short of expectations, which is assumed to be due to the restructuring of the written exam. Improved results are expected in the future terms as soon as students become more familiar with the new system and exam format. Long-term effects, such as a deeper understanding of mathematical concepts and better preparation for advanced courses, cannot yet be estimated after just one term, but are expected to be positive.

References

- Brown, P. C., Roediger, H. L., and McDaniel, M. A. (2014) *Make it stick: The science of successful learning*. Harvard University Press.
- Roediger, H. L. and Butler, A. C. (2011) The critical role of retrieval practice in long-term retention. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*, 15(1), 20-27.
- Sotola, L.K. and Crede, M. (2021) Regarding Class Quizzes: a Meta-analytic Synthesis of Studies on the Relationship Between Frequent Low-Stakes Testing and Class Performance. *Educational Psychology Review*, 33:407-426